

POST-PANDEMIC LEARNING LOSS AND RECOVERY STRATEGIES AMONG SECONDARY AND HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS IN KARACHI, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Education has faced subsequent disturbance due to the COVID-19 and the floods of 2022 enhances the setback of education in Pakistan. The study focuses and evaluates different recovery strategies implemented in schools of Karachi, especially the secondary and the higher secondary schools which are first steps for the students towards the professional degrees and to attain higher education. Employing mixed-method approach in combination of quantitative analysis and with the sample size of $n = 420$ students and qualitative interviews of $n = 12$ teaching staff found out that an average core subjects' academic performance has declined at an average of 23% and the most affected subjects at this level have been mathematics and English. An average of 12% recovery gains and measurable enhancement has been represented through measures taken like; blending learning, integrated studies, peer coaching and tutoring, remedial classes and online assistance (Smith et al., 2022; Johnson & Alvarez, 2021).

UNESCO, 2023; Zhao, 2022 stated the same findings in the post-pandemic education recovery research, in which online and physical learning environment and remedial model peer and group assistance in studies displayed a significant role and contributed to a remarkable level in recovery trends in educational loss but the inequality and difference in provision of facilities, digital support, teachers' training, investment on learning infrastructure in public and private sector become a barrier in equitable and sustainable recovery at the level of secondary and higher secondary studies (OECD, 2022; Malik & Rehman, 2023; Anderson et al., 2023; World Bank, 2022).

INTRODUCTION

Education all over the world was triggered to face one of the largest disruptions in the human history and it directly and indirectly affected more than 1.6 billion students globally (UNESCO, 2022). Closure of schools from March 2020 to Mid-2021 in Pakistan remained one of the miserable effects and a setback to the education and the floods 2022 further intervened it quite badly (World Bank, 2023) and Karachi despite being one of the most populous city practiced long closure of

educational institutions especially the secondary and higher secondary school, resulting in promotion of students to next grades without examination, which really hurt the learning abilities of students and put a gap of knowledge. The study loss has been highlighted in the provincial reports but there is very little effort made on post-pandemic recovery strategies particularly in the public sector and it further makes it difficult for students of SSC and HSC

to clear admission test in the universities and in other institution of graduating education.

This study aims to:

1. Enumerated the degree of learning loss among SSC and HSC students in Karachi post-pandemic.
2. Identified and evaluated strategies schools employed to recover learning outcomes.
3. Explored teachers' and students' perceptions of the effectiveness of these strategies.

Mix-method design enabled the researchers to bridge quantitative measurement of learning outcomes with a blend of qualitative insights from all the stakeholders.

2. Literature Review

- Studies in the recent past have confirmed that there has been a widespread setback in the field of education due to closure of schools during the pandemic. 20 - 25% reduction of learning has been estimated in researchers from the Netherlands (Engzell et al., 2021) and the U.S. (Kuhfeld et al., 2022) especially in the areas where the COVID SOP needed most to be implemented. Both technological divides and socioeconomic disparities face these losses. A report from the World Bank (2023) estimated that the ratio of illiteracy has increased since the proportion of last 10 years which said that a simple text reading deficiency rose from 57% to 70% worldwide and the countries in the South Asia are among the hardest and worst hit regions.

- All levels of educational institutions faced substantial setback across Pakistan during the COVID. A report by the ASER (2023) shows that about 70% of students from grade 8 remained unable to solve some basic mathematics sums of their level. In addition, the drop out ratio increased rapidly especially in the cases of female students (Malik & Jamil, 2022). Studies of (Riaz et al., 2023; Shah & Iqbal, 2024) emphasized that only elite schools kept the teaching and learning process continue through digital modes and for other stakeholders the lack of infrastructure and availability of digital support prolonged a gap of studies among students even the case was not much satisfactory in Karachi and other big cities.

- UNICEF, 2023 reported that hybrid teaching and learning system, remedial education, targeted tutoring and focused studies enabled a decent recovery among the students globally. It was quite evident that the trained educationists made a mark in delivering their lectures and lessons in various small-group tuition cases and structured catch-up programmes (The Education Foundation, 2022).

- Summer remedial classes, shortening the syllabus and extra online coaching classes were a few initiatives taken by the government and the private sector as joint venture to repair the loss. Additionally online platforms like Taleem Ghar and Sindh Virtual School played a pivotal role in reducing the study gap (Hassan & Afzal, 2024). Comparison of Pakistan with other countries during the pandemic and delivering in the field of education especially at the SSC and HSC levels has a huge gap. Most of the work in Pakistan remained limited to primary education as the government had announced to promote all grades to the next level without any exams. The current study addressed this gap and proved an assessment with evidence about the losses and the effort made by all stakeholders to recover.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The current study used the mix method design which was the best fit to investigate and analyze score with qualitative interviews to provide an in-depth understanding about the issue.

Quantitative data measured the degree of learning loss through standardized assessments in English, Mathematics, and Science.

Qualitative data explored insights of recovery programs through semi-structured interviews with teachers and students.

3.2 Population and Sample

420 students from six different schools (3 each from private and public sector) were selected for the quantitative sampling and 12 teachers and 15 students participated from the same schools for the interview in qualitative part. The targeted population for the study remained students for grade 9 to 12. Representation across gender, sector and socioeconomic background was

assisted through a stratified random sampling technique.

3.3 Instruments

1. **Achievement Tests** - Standardized assessments aligned with Sindh Board curriculum for English, Mathematics, and Science (50 marks each).
2. **Teacher & Student Interview Guides** - Semi-structured questions exploring perceptions of learning loss, challenges, and recovery efforts.
3. **Observation Checklists** - For classroom recovery strategies (remedial classes, digital support, peer tutoring).

3.4 Data Collection

Months from February to May 2024 were used to collect the data for the study. The schools cooperated in sharing examination record of their student, which included pre-pandemic (2019) and post-pandemic (2023) data. Later standardized conditions were utilized for the

follow-up assessments, questionnaire and interview proforma. All interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim.

Data were collected between February and May 2024. Schools provided pre-pandemic (2019) and post-pandemic (2023) examination records. Follow-up assessments were conducted by the researcher under standardized conditions.

3.5 Data Analysis

- **Quantitative:** Paired-sample t-tests compared pre- and post-pandemic mean scores.
 - **Qualitative:** Thematic analysis identified recurring patterns regarding recovery strategies and challenges.
- Ethical considerations for the research were kept intact as per the research ethics and all the participants showed their consent before the participation.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Quantitative Findings

Table 1: Mean Scores Comparison (Pre- and Post-Pandemic)

Subject	Mean Score 2019	Mean Score 2023	Mean Difference	% Change	p-value
English	71.2	54.5	-16.7	-23.5%	0.001
Mathematics	68.5	50.4	-18.1	-26.4%	0.000
Science	73.4	60.2	-13.2	-18.0%	0.004
Overall Average	71.0	55.0	-16.0	-22.5%	0.001

Above stats clearly define that there is a significant decline in the performance of students in all subjects ($p < 0.05$). The highest loss (-26%) has been observed in the subject of Mathematics which suffered the most, the reliability check has been confirmed in a global finding (Kuhfeld et al., 2022).

Table 2: Recovery Gains after Remedial Interventions (Six-Month Follow-up)

Intervention Type	Participants (n)	Mean Intervention	Pre- Mean Intervention	Post-Improvement (%)
Remedial Classes	150	52.8	61.0	+15.5%
Peer Tutoring	120	54.5	60.3	+10.7%

Intervention Type	Participants (n)	Mean Intervention	Pre- Mean Intervention	Post-Improvement (%)
Blended Learning	150	56.0	63.4	+13.2%
Combined Average	420	54.4	61.6	+13.2%

The programmes like remedial classes and other recovery plans contributed positively as shown in the table and a marked improvement is seen. Since the private institutions own better and stronger technology integration system with trained workforce the impact was more vivid in this sector.

4.2 Qualitative Findings

The researchers ended up with three major themes emerged from the interviews taken from the participants.

Theme 1: Academic Deterioration

According to the closed observation from the educators a noticeable decline has been shown in the students’ performances, especially in regard to conceptual understanding, reading comprehensions and writing skills.

“The toppers till 2020 feel hesitant in solving simple sums and almost unable to collect back their analytical thinking skills to draft essays”. (Teacher, public school)

Theme 2: Unequal Access

It was an opinion of number of students in the public schools that there has been a huge difference in provision of facilities like; internet access, mobile, laptop or other communication devices. On the other hand, the students of private schools not only had easy access to all, they were provided with proper gadgets, decent transportation and all safety measures required during and after the pandemic.

Theme 3: Retrieval and Motivation

A blended and gradual improvement was observed through peer tutoring, group coaching, one on one discussions, lectures sharing thought different mediums, but overall motivation, encouragement and support from the parents and government did not match according to desire and need of the students.

4.3 Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Results

The mixed-method allowed the researchers to experience cross-validation. The quantitative data measured the loss of studies and the qualitative insights clarified the question like *why* something happened and *how* difficult it remained for one group (public sector) to complete the recovery and one the other hand, it seemed much better for the elite schools and the well-off parents to arrange quality education even in the worst times of life.

5. Conclusion

It is evident from the study that there has been a significant loss among the students of SSC and HSC in the Karachi region which averages to 22 – 26% loss across all subject. Despite a modest overall improvement was observed through blended strategies the gap of providing equal facilities injured complete recovery. The study suggests that there has been an urgent need for diagnostic assessments, training of teachers especially to learn technology, inclusion of digitalization in our educational system and overall support. The delays may increase the level of risking gaps of learning, and an expected

turmoil in the long-term socio-economic format which may become a gigantic disadvantage for the youth in the life to come for equally competing in all fields if life.

6. Recommendations

1. There is a need to establish remedial portions in the academic calendar for facing any unexpected challenges
2. Introduction of differentiated instructions methods and diagnostic assessment has become need of an hour
3. Equal opportunities should be provided to all stakeholders especially the students to access internet, communication devices and content platforms.
4. A monitoring system should be developed at all the district levels to track the recovery process in all public and private institutions.
5. Hybrid teaching may be introduced in all schools which should combine online classes and face-to-face learning facilities.
6. Counseling sessions, mentorship programmes and awareness programmes should be part of government's policy for motivating students and improving their overall well-being.

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